

METHODOLOGY FOR USING INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH IN THE SYSTEM OF CONTINUING EDUCATION

¹Rajappa B, ²Subhadhanuraja, ³Cuddapah.Dhanajaya Rao, ⁴Jayabharath Reddy

¹Professor and Head, Department of Fundamental sciences, Sambhram University, Jizzax,

²Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies, Sambhram University, Jizzax,

³Associate Professor, Department of Physics, Sambhram University, Jizzax, ⁴Assistant Professor,
Department of Computer Science, Sambhram University, Jizzax

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11498476>

Abstract. *The Methodology for using international research and teaching methods is highly significant in the context of continuing education, since the competitiveness of modern teachers depends on the quality of the continuing education process. The purpose of the article is to analyze the experience of using innovative research in international level and methods in the system of continuing education by using different methodologies. The article presents the experience of organizing the work of students using modern forms and methods of advanced training. Training activities contribute to the intensification of the learning process. It is aimed both at mastering the cognitive component of the information transmitted by the teacher, and the formation of new professional models of behavior that meet modern requirements for the implementation of pedagogical activity.*

Keywords: *advanced training, professional retraining, design activities, training. Continuing education.*

Introduction

Analyzing the development trends in professional education, there is a clear demand for professional retraining and advanced training courses. The adoption of new Federal state educational standards, the informatization of education, and advancements in science and technology necessitate the creation of new professional fields within professional and pedagogical activities (Gladkov et al., 2019). Ongoing teacher education is crucial for their professional growth, competitiveness, mobility, and demand in the job market (Klinkov, 2018).

This article examines the practices used to prepare students for innovation through academic courses, Examples of such courses include "Theory, Practice and Methods of Teaching in an Educational Organization" and "Current Problems of Smart Education."

Currently, the professional faculty development programme is aligned with students job demands. These courses cater to teachers at various educational levels, including preschool. For instance, the course "Innovative teaching and research strategies" is specifically designed for higher education educators.

Professional retraining involves developing additional competencies necessary to perform new professional functions or to acquire additional qualifications, utilizing modern methods that enhance the learning process (Vaskovskaya, 2018; Vaganova et al., 2019a).

Professional development focuses on updating students theoretical and practical knowledge to master innovative approaches to solving professional challenges (Pichugina & Bondarchuk, 2019).

At Sambhram University, Uzbekistan diverse methods are employed in training students as a part of academic courses. These methods include round tables, discussion clubs, masterclasses, workshops, and consultations. To meet the updated requirements for professional

retraining and advanced training, innovative forms and methods are being introduced. These include training activities and video conferences, mental maps, project-based activities, and other innovative approaches.

Theoretical Framework

Our study relies on the findings of researchers who explored professional retraining and further training as integral components of lifelong education.

The growing demand for educational services aimed at professional retraining necessitates enhancements in current practices of advanced training and professional retraining (Fix & Troshchinskiy, 2015), as well as the exploration of contemporary forms and methods for delivering the educational process (Grigoriev et al., 2019).

Methodology

The study on continuing higher education (CHE) in European Countries presents findings at three distinct levels: system, institutional, and program.

System Level At the system level, the study provides an overview of the foundational concepts of continuing education in European Countries, explaining the framework conditions that shape CHE. This includes policies, regulations, and the overall structure of the continuing education system in the country.

On the **Institutional Level**, the study examines the organizational structures and management practices of CHE. It covers several key areas:

1. **Quality Assurance:** Methods and standards for maintaining and improving the quality of continuing education programs.
2. **Publicity and Marketing:** Strategies for promoting continuing education programs to potential participants.
3. **Funding:** Sources and management of financial resources for continuing education.
4. **Participants:** Demographics and characteristics of individuals enrolled in continuing education programs.

At the **program level**, the study provides detailed information about various aspects of continuing education courses:

1. **Course Types:** Descriptions of the different types of courses offered within continuing education.
2. **Formal Aspects:** Administrative and procedural details related to continuing education programs.
3. **Staff Motivation:** Factors influencing the motivation of staff involved in delivering continuing education.
4. **Partnerships:** Collaborations with other institutions, organizations, or industries to enhance the effectiveness of continuing education.

Results and Discussions

The research was conducted based on the Sambhram University in the city of Jizzax as part of Professional retraining

course for teachers. The work was carried out in 2024.

Some classes are conducted in-person, while others are held remotely. The online video conference format facilitates the sharing of best practices and the acquisition of new, pertinent information on educational matters.

Video conferences follow specific rules and are designed to achieve particular goals and objectives. Researchers participate in these sessions, allowing them to ask questions, share opinions, and receive recommendations.

In professional development, the use of mental maps is particularly valuable. Mental maps provide a logical structure for information, facilitating its rapid comprehension. Students create mental associations starting from a central object. Through project activities, students enhance their professional skills, discover innovative solutions to problems, and assess the practicality and effectiveness of project ideas.

Students work in subgroups to develop step-by-step guides divided into blocks. Creating mental maps is often done on the electronic learning platform Moodle, where students can utilize various creative solutions, such as colors and images, to define central concepts and ideas, which then branch out into related ideas, concepts, and actions. This process helps students form a holistic understanding of the activity by working with sequences, lists, and numbers. Mental maps focus on identifying a main concept from which ideas, tasks, thoughts, and necessary steps for a specific project stem.

- **What formats and techniques have proven most effective during the learning process?**

- **What forms and methods were utilized?**

Developing mental maps helps teachers organize relationships between individual topics, highlight controversial issues, and effectively evaluate activities including planning, execution, monitoring, and presenting project work. Students in advanced training courses frequently use mental maps to study teaching methods in various fields, employing specific technologies, methods, and tools.

During project activities, students enhance their theoretical knowledge and develop practical skills.

Results of statistical processing of survey data

We may infer from the data collected that students are aware of the high caliber of project activities and the application of mental maps. It is emphasized how important training exercises and video conferences are. Based on observations,

The audience believes that the training activity is the most effective type of instruction, setting it apart from the main mass.

Training often consists of lectures, project activities, and mental maps. Meanwhile, the audience feels that using mental maps on a regular basis improves training outcomes. You can increase the amount of training chances for students by using mental maps, videoconferencing, and thorough project and training activity execution.

Conclusion

We are aware of the experience with utilizing cutting-edge formats and techniques in the student advanced training and professional retraining system. The most successful training techniques among them included mental mapping, project-based learning, and video conferences. You can organize material into chunks by using mental maps, which helps you memorize things better. It is not necessary for students to read a lot of textual material. Students can develop their professional competence, come up with novel, unconventional solutions to challenges, and assess the viability and efficacy of project ideas through project activity. Students can ask questions of top professionals, receive recommendations, and learn about best practices in the industry by using video conferences to communicate pertinent information. Training exercises also have the benefit of being practically oriented. Its goals are to help students master the cognitive portion of the knowledge that their teachers impart and to help them adopt new professional behaviours.

REFERENCES

1. Andrienko, O.A. (2019a). On the need to apply gaming training technologies. *Balkan Scientific Review*, 2(4), 5-8
2. Cirdan, A.P. (2019). Innovative technologies of professional training of future economists in the system of continuous education. *Humanitarian Balkan Research*, 2(4), 27-30.
3. Filchenkova, I.F. (2019). Educational management of innovative activity of teachers as an object of pedagogical research. *Vestnik of Minin University*, 7(4).
4. Fix, N. P., & Troshchinskiy, V. V. (2015). Business game to eliminate violations of the normal operation of the power system. *Business Game on Elimination of an Emergency in the Electric Power System. Modern problems of science and education*, 1 (part 1).
5. Grigoriev, S. G., Shabunina, V. A., Tsarapkina, Ju. M., & Dunaeva, N. V. (2019). Electronic library system as a means of self-development of students of digital generation Z (on the example of studying the course "Basics of the counselor activity"). *Scientific and technical libraries*, 7, 78-99. 29.
6. Pichugina, G.A., & Bondarchuk, A.I. (2019). Structure of the training case in the organization of the educational process. *Humanitarian Balkan Research*, 2(4), 5-7.
7. Ponachugin, A.V., & Lapygin, Yu.N. (2019). Digital educational resources of the university: design, analysis and expertise. *Vestnik of Minin University*, 7(2), 5.
8. Slastenin, V.A., Podymova, L.S. (2007). The readiness of the teacher to innovate / *Siberian Pedagogical Journal*. 1, 42-49
9. Raven, J. (2017). Education and Sociocybernetics. *Azimuth of Scientific Researches: Economics and Management*, 6, 3(20), 289-2
10. Trifonova, S. A. (2011). Diagnostics of the formation of teachers' readiness for the implementation of innovative activity. *Actual problems of pedagogy: materials of the Intern. in absentia scientific conf. Young Scientist Publishing House*, 211.
11. Tsarapkina, Ju. M., Dunaeva, N. V., & Kireicheva, A. M. (2019b). Application of BYOD technology in education on the example of Lecture Racing mobile application. *Informatics and Education*, 9(308), 56-64.

12. Vaganova, O.I., Odarich, I.N., Popkova, A.A., Smirnova, Z.V., & Lebedeva, A.A. (2019b). Independent work of students in professional educational institutions. *Amazonia Investiga*, 8 (22), 295 – 304. <https://www.amazoniainvestiga.info/index.php/amazonia/article/view/447>
13. Vaskovskaya, G.A. (2018). Features of implementation of pedagogical technologies of profile training. *Balkan Scientific Review*, 1, 76-79.